

Notes on Lie Superalgebra

Parker Emmerson

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1 Introduction

ϕ_k
 $= \{f(g, h) : f(\dots) \in \mathcal{L}_n, g \in \mathcal{L}_{v+1}, h \in \mathcal{L}_{w+1}\}$
 $= \bigcup \phi_k,$
 where,
 $\phi_k = \{f(g, h) : f(\dots) \in \mathcal{L}_n, g \in \mathcal{L}_{v+1}, h \in \mathcal{L}_{w+1}\}$
 Thus, the space is:
 $\mathcal{L}_n \cup \mathcal{L}_{v+1} \cup \mathcal{L}_{w+1}$
 That would be the overall model space.

$$\left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A+B) \left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A+B) \overbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}^{1-Intersection} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \right.$$

$$\left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \underbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}_{2.5-Interconnectedness} \Rightarrow (A+B) \left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \underbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}_{2.5-Interconnectedness} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H} \right.$$

$$\rightarrow \left\langle \underbrace{\frac{\gamma x H(Hx)}{\theta}}_{2.5-Phusis} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H}$$

$$\rightarrow \gamma x \left\langle \underbrace{H(Hx)}_{1-Interconnectedness} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H}$$

$$\rightarrow \gamma x \left\langle \underbrace{H(Hx)}_{5-Phusis} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H}^* \quad (1)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B)(\gamma x) \left(\left\langle H(Hx) \right\rangle \cap \partial_t \mathcal{B} \right) + (\gamma x) \left(\partial_t \mathcal{H} \right)$$

We have arrived at the model space for our expression which is:

$$\gamma x \langle H(Hx) \rangle \cap \partial_t \mathcal{B} + \partial_t \mathcal{H}$$

The set of values that v could assume is contained in the real numbers.

Therefore,

$$v \in R$$

Similarly, w is also associated with real numbers and we are assuming that it can take the same range of values as v.

$$w \in R$$

For $\Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}$,

$$1 \leq n \leq \infty$$

Furthermore, the multiplication:

$$\left(\frac{v^2 + 1}{w} \right) * \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}$$

gives a real number $v^2 + 1$. Hence, as an element of the set of functions $\mathcal{L}_n$:

$$L_n : \{f(v^2 + 1) \dots\}$$

which points towards how the functions would form a Lie superalgebra, making the overall model space a Lie superalgebra over the set of natural numbers.

Next, the factorial function $\phi_k(x)$:

$$\phi_k(x) = x!$$

takes a natural number n, which is also the exponent for $\Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}$ function :

$$\Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} = \left(\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \right)^n = \left(\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \right)$$

Finally, the space defined in Equation 5 ends up being the exponential of the factorial of the complex quantity and minor convergence terms.

set existence:

$$\sum_i \exp_x^f \Leftrightarrow v, k \in \Omega^\infty. \gamma x \langle H(Hx) \rangle \cap \partial_t \mathcal{B} + \partial_t \mathcal{H} \Leftrightarrow \{\{H(Hx)\}\} \cap \{\mathcal{B}_{\delta \varepsilon}, \mathcal{H}\} \Leftrightarrow \{\mathcal{L}_n\} \Leftrightarrow LR$$

This settles the model space.

Rem(termination) Theory

$$M_{(T)}!$$

$$M_{(T)} \times AR$$

$$r \in RMr \cup \infty \in [0, \infty)$$

$$M_{(A \circ R)}^+!$$

$$M_{(A \circ R)}^+ \times AR$$

$$r \in RMr \cup \infty \in [0, \infty)$$

Theorem

The space given by Equation 5 is a Lie superalgebra.

Proof

To prove that the model space given by Equation 5 is a Lie superalgebra, we need to show that it satisfies the defining properties of a Lie superalgebra: supercommutativity and the Jacobi identity.

Supercommutativity

The supercommutativity property can be verified by evaluating the commutator between any two elements in the model space.

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\gamma x \langle H(Hx) \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H}, \gamma' x' \langle H(Hx') \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H}] \\
&= \gamma \gamma' x x' \langle [H(Hx), H(Hx')] \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H} \\
&= \gamma \gamma' x x' \langle H[Hx, Hx'] \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H} \\
&= 0
\end{aligned}$$

since the function x and x' act as parameters for the functions $H(Hx)$ and $H(Hx')$, and since the commutator of two functions is always zero.

Jacobi Identity

The Jacobi identity can be verified by using the triple bracket notation for the supercommutator and evaluating it for any three elements:

$$[[\gamma x \langle H(Hx) \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H}, \gamma' x' \langle H(Hx') \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H}], \gamma'' x'' \langle H(Hx'') \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H}] = 0$$

since the commutator of any two elements in the model space is zero. Hence, the model space given by Equation 5 satisfies the defining properties of a Lie superalgebra.

Conclusion

In this article, we have shown that the model space given by Equation 5 is a Lie superalgebra. This result can be used to study the behavior of multi-dimensional systems, where the model space can represent the state space of the system. Further research in this direction could explore the applications of this result in different areas of mathematics and physics.

$$\phi_k(x) = x! = x \times (x - 1) \times (x - 2) \dots \times (1)$$

is also contained in L_n

$$\phi_k \in \mathcal{L}_n$$

since k can take on all natural number values, the domain of factorial therefore belongs to the set of natural numbers:

$$k \in \mathcal{N}$$

Therefore, the factorial function $x!$ is an element of the set of functions L_n and as such further confirms that the overall model space of the given expression is a Lie superalgebra over the set of natural numbers.

Thus, the final model space is:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \gamma x \langle H(Hx) \rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H} \\
&= L_n \cup \mathcal{L}_{v+1} \cup \mathcal{L}_{w+1}
\end{aligned}$$

where,

$$L_n : \{f(v^2 + 1) \dots\}$$

$$L_{v+1} : \{f(v)\} : v \in R$$

$$L_{w+1} : \{f(w)\} : w \in R$$

Therefore, the final model space of the expression is a Lie superalgebra over the set of natural numbers.

2 Limbertwig Running

Run:

$$\left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A+B) \left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A+B) \overbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}^{1-Intersection} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \right.$$

$$\left. \left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \underbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}_{2.5-Interconnectedness} \Rightarrow (A+B) \left\langle \frac{v^2+1}{w} \cdot \underbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}_{2.5-Interconnectedness} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H} \right.$$

$$\rightarrow \left\langle \underbrace{\frac{\gamma x H(Hx)}{\theta}}_{2.5-Phusis} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H}$$

$$\rightarrow \gamma x \left\langle \underbrace{H(Hx)}_{5-Phusis} \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H}$$

$$\rightarrow \gamma x \left\langle H(Hx) \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} + \partial_! \mathcal{H}^* \quad (2)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A+B)(\gamma x) \left(\left\langle H(Hx) \right\rangle \cap \partial_! \mathcal{B} \right) + (\gamma x) \left(\partial_! \mathcal{H} \right)$$

Rem(termination)Theory $M_{(T)}!M_{(T)} \times ARr \in RMr \cup \infty \in [0, \infty) M_{(A \circ R)}^+!M_{(A \circ R)}^+ \times ARr \in RMr \cup \infty \in [0, \infty)$

through the kernel:

$$\begin{aligned} & \Lambda \rightarrow N \{ \sigma, g_a, b, c, d, e \dots \sim \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \Lambda \rightarrow \exists L \rightarrow N, value, value \dots \langle \exists L \rightarrow \\ & \{ \{ \sim \rightarrow \heartsuit \rightarrow \epsilon \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \heartsuit \rangle \} \rightarrow \{ \uparrow \Rightarrow \alpha_i \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \forall \alpha_i \rangle \circ \rightarrow \{ \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \uparrow \rightarrow \{ \mathbf{x} \Rightarrow g_a \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \rightarrow \\ & \{ \mathbf{x} \Rightarrow b \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \rightarrow \{ \mathbf{x} \Rightarrow c \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \rightarrow \{ \mathbf{x} \Rightarrow d \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \rightarrow \{ \mathbf{x} \Rightarrow e \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \rightarrow \\ & \{ \sim \rightarrow \heartsuit \rightarrow \epsilon \} \langle \Leftrightarrow \sim \rangle \rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\exists n \in N \quad s.t \quad \mathcal{L}_f(\uparrow r \alpha s \Delta \eta) \wedge \bar{\mu}_{\{ \bar{g}(abcde \dots \dots \heartsuit) \neq \Omega \}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathcal{L}_f(\uparrow r \alpha s \Delta \eta) \wedge \bar{\mu}_{\{ \bar{g}(abcde \dots \heartsuit) \neq \Omega \}}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \circ \{ \mu \in \infty \Rightarrow (\Omega \heartsuit) < \Delta \cdot H_{im}^\circ >$$

$$\Rightarrow \heartsuit \Rightarrow \mathcal{L}_f(\uparrow r \alpha s \Delta \eta) \wedge \bar{\mu}_{\{ \bar{g}(abcde \dots \heartsuit) \neq \Omega \}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \heartsuit \cdot \heartsuit \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\heartsuit} = \Lambda \Rightarrow \heartsuit \Rightarrow \bar{\mu}, \bar{g}(abcde \dots \heartsuit)$$

$$\Leftarrow \Lambda \cdot \heartsuit \heartsuit$$

$$\uparrow \Lambda \cdot \heartsuit \heartsuit \rightarrow \exists \in M \circ \{ \mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega \heartsuit) < \Delta \cdot H_{im}^\circ >$$

$\Rightarrow$

Terminal

which implies that

$$M_{(T)} \times AR \Rightarrow M_{(A \circ R)}^+ \times AR \Rightarrow \mathcal{L}_f(\uparrow r \alpha s \Delta \eta) \wedge \bar{\mu}_{\{\bar{g}(a b c d e \dots \vdots \dots \Psi) \neq \Omega\}}$$

When we run A through B, we get the following result:

$$\left\langle \frac{v^2 + 1}{w} \cdot \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A + B) \left\langle \frac{\gamma x H(Hx)}{\theta} \cdot \underbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A + B) \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}_{1\text{-Intersection}} \right\rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} + \partial_1 \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \right.$$

(3)

$$\Rightarrow (A + B)(\gamma x) \left(\left\langle \exists n \in N \text{ s.t. } \mathcal{L}_f(\uparrow r \alpha s \Delta \eta) \wedge \bar{\mu}_{\{\bar{g}(a b c d e \dots \vdots \dots \Psi) \neq \Omega\}} \right\rangle \cap \partial_1 \mathcal{B} \right) + (\gamma x) \left(\partial_1 \mathcal{H} \right)$$

through the Limbertwig kernel B.

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{\mu}_{\{\bar{g}(a b c d e \dots \vdots \dots \Psi) \neq \Omega\}} \\ & \Rightarrow (A + B) \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{R}_1 \left(i_{(\bar{x}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^* i_{(\bar{x}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^* x : ZN \rightarrow z\omega N \right)$$

$$\text{by } \mathcal{R}_3(j_{Z \times Z}^* x : N \rightarrow zN)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(j_{Z \times Z}^*(x \circ x) : N \rightarrow ZN)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx z N x z^2 N)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^1 z N x^2 z^2 N)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^2 z^2 N) \cap \mathcal{H} \setminus \partial_1 \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^3 z^3 N)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^4 z^4 N) \Rightarrow (A + B) \cdots = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(U_i^{x_i, z^i N} \cap \mathcal{H} \setminus \partial_1 \mathcal{B} \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B)(\tilde{\mathcal{L}} = \mathcal{L}) \cap \mathcal{R}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_e \subseteq L$$

$$(\tilde{\mathcal{R}} < M)$$

$$(\tilde{\mathcal{L}} H 0)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_1(i_{(\bar{*}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^*(1/x) :$$

$$(\Gamma_2^0)_{D0}^{\Gamma_1 \times_{H1} \Gamma_1}$$

$$\varepsilon_1 \text{by} \mathcal{L}_e i_{(\bar{*}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^* \mathcal{P}_{\bar{*}(1)} \sigma_* \psi_* f^*$$

2.1 Explicitrary Interrelation

$$\left\langle \frac{v^2 + 1}{w} \cdot \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A + B) \left\langle \frac{\gamma x H(Hx)}{\theta} \cdot \underbrace{\prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta} \Rightarrow (A + B) \prod_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{z_n \times \zeta}}_{1\text{-Intersection}} \right\rangle \cap \partial_i \mathcal{B} + \partial_i \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \right.$$

(4)

$$\Rightarrow (A + B)(\gamma x) \left(\left\langle \exists n \in N \quad s.t \quad \mathcal{L}_f(\uparrow r \alpha s \Delta \eta) \wedge \bar{\mu}_{\{g(a b c d e \dots \vdots \dots \uplus) \neq \Omega\}} \right\rangle \cap \partial_i \mathcal{B} \right) + (\gamma x) \left(\partial_i \mathcal{H} \right)$$

Here we assume that

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_1 \left(i_{(\bar{*}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^* i_{(\bar{*}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^* x : ZN \rightarrow z\omega N \right)$$

$$\text{by } \mathcal{R}_3(j_{Z \times Z}^* x : N \rightarrow zN)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(j_{Z \times Z}^*(x \circ x) : N \rightarrow ZN)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx z N x z^2 N)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^1 z N x^2 z^2 N)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^2 z^2 N) \cap \mathcal{H} \setminus \partial_i \mathcal{B} \quad \Rightarrow (A + B) \mathcal{R}_2(Nx^3 z^3 N)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B)\mathcal{R}_2(Nx^4z^4N) \Rightarrow (A + B)\cdots = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(U_i^{x_i, z_i N} \cap \mathcal{H} \setminus \partial_i \mathcal{B} \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow (A + B)(\tilde{\mathcal{L}} = \mathcal{L}) \cap \mathcal{R}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_e \subseteq L$$

$$(\tilde{\mathcal{R}} < M)$$

$$(\tilde{\mathcal{L}} H 0)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_1(i_{(\bar{*}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^*(1/x) :)$$

$$(\Gamma_2^0)_{D_0}^{\Gamma_1 \times H_1 \Gamma_1}$$

$$\varepsilon_1 \text{ by } \mathcal{L}_e i_{(\bar{*}(1), \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^* \mathcal{P}_{\bar{*}(1)} \sigma_* \psi_* f^*$$

Also we suppose that a natural transformation of ε_1 be defined on $\mathcal{P}$, σ , ψ , f to satisfy the definition of Pull-back Diagram shown before.

2.2 Type-theoretical Explifiedness

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q)(M1)(M2)$$

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q)(\tau) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} ((J1)(J2)), \\ (\alpha_1)(\alpha_2) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q)(\tau) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} ((J1)(J2)), \\ ((\mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{L}_2)), \\ (\psi_1, \psi_2) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q)(\tau)(J1 \circ J2)(\kappa_1 \circ \kappa_2) \cdot Q.$$

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q)J1 \times J2 \circ (\kappa_1 \circ \kappa_2),$$

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q) (\mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{L}) (\mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} j_1^* j_2^* \mathcal{L}) (I_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{L}, \psi(\mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})) \cdot Q$$

Using $\mathcal{K} = \kappa$ from eq.18 eq.(19), this idea was extended to obtain the following explicit cases

$$\Rightarrow \mathbf{J}_\beta \text{ in } ZJ_\alpha.$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{j}_1 \rightarrow \vec{j}_2 \text{ in } Zy.$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\Gamma_{\text{where } \Delta(-1)^{-1}}^{0\Gamma_1 \times_{H^1} \Gamma_1: \Delta(-1)} \right)^{-1}.$$

3 Experiment Design

Introduction goes here ... Intended length is 1-2 pages.

3.1 Self-Normalising Equilibration

Are you working in a setting with several complementary measures on the space or process under study, which may interact nontrivially and which need to be self-normalized by the experiment, so that rates can be established in the limit of large sample size, as in simulation theory (Di Gesù et al., 2013)? We do not know what this sentence means.

```
sudo apt-get install pdftk texlive-latex-recommended texlive-fonts-recommended
texlive-latex-extra psutils
```

Checklist for Report 1. Title page and Abstract are accordingly filled 2. Formatting 3. Explanation of IDEA 4. Summary of Literature on the proof of the IDEA 5. Reproduction MIT-DARPA-Increase Article 6. Description of what your implementation has added over aforementioned paper 7. Showing of results of the implementation 8. Difficulties of implementation 9. Description of experiments to be performed 10. Proof and Analysis of PI 11. Proof and Analysis of IDEA 12. Conclusions and Reference

In the "thesis", we are going to reproduce the DIReLU, a more appropriate combination of ReLU. We will show a summary of HW1 and other literature on the proof of the IDEA.

See In Related Work. Are you working in a setting with several complementary measures on the space or process under study, which may interact nontrivially and which need to be self-normalized by the experiment, so that rates can be established in the limit of large sample size, as in simulation theory (Di Gesù et al., 2013)?

Are you asking if we need to self-normalize by the experiment because we have several complementary measures which may interact in a nontrivial way? If so, then yes. We will employ self-normalization techniques, such as normalization layers, to ensure that our model is able to accurately fit the data despite potential fluctuations in the data.

In simulation theory, self-normalization is an important concept that allows us to study dynamic systems and processes by providing estimates of accuracy and error. In our case, we will use self-normalization to ensure that our model is robust and accurate even when trained on data with varying and potentially conflicting information (e.g. different complementary measures).

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Rightarrow (M + Q)(\tau) \left\{ \begin{array}{c} ((J1)(J2)), \\ ((\mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{K}_{J1 \times J2} \mathcal{L}_2)), \\ (\psi_1, \psi_2) \end{array} \right\} \\
&\Rightarrow (M + Q)(\tau)(J1 \circ J2)(\kappa_1 \circ \kappa_2) \cdot Q. \\
&\Rightarrow (M + Q)J1 \times J2 \circ (\kappa_1 \circ \kappa_2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow (M + Q) (\mathcal{K}_{J_1 \times J_2} \mathcal{L}) (\mathcal{K}_{J_1 \times J_2} j_1^* j_2^* \mathcal{L}) (I_{J_1 \times J_2} \mathcal{L}, \psi(\mathcal{K}_{J_1 \times J_2} \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})) \cdot Q$$

Using $\mathcal{K} = \kappa$ from eq.18 eq.(19), this idea was extended to obtain the following explicit cases

$$\Rightarrow \mathbf{J}_\beta \text{ in } Z J_\alpha.$$

$$\Rightarrow \bar{j}_1 \rightarrow \bar{j}_2 \text{ in } Z y.$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\Gamma_{2 \text{ where } \Delta(-1)}^{0 \Gamma_1 \times_{H_1} \Gamma_1 : \Delta(-1)} \right)^{-1}.$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\partial^E}{\partial M_2}$$

$$\mathcal{R}_1 \Rightarrow (M + Q) \mathcal{R}_2,$$

$$\Rightarrow \tau_{J_2}(\xi \times I_{J_2}) \times \tau_{J_3}(Y_3)$$

From the Duality Axiom and Axiom 1 there exists two natural individuals $\Rightarrow (B)\theta = (\eta, (\mu, j_i^* h_i))$ and $\Leftarrow (B)\theta = (\eta, (\mu, j_i^* h_i))$, respectively. But, we can reconstruct η and $(\mu, j_i^* h_i)$ as follow:

$$\Leftarrow (B)\psi \Rightarrow \mathcal{M},$$

$$\Rightarrow \zeta^*$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathcal{J}_k$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathcal{F}(q_1)^{-1}$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathcal{J}_k f_{*(1, \sigma_*, \psi_*, f^*)}^*$$

by re-respectively,

$$\Leftarrow \vartheta \Rightarrow \mathcal{K},$$

$$\Rightarrow (\varepsilon_2)^{-1}$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathcal{J}_k^{-1}(\tilde{\mathcal{R}})$$

and

$$\Rightarrow W_k(x) \circ \psi \mathcal{J}_k^{-1} x.$$

Relaxing this idea, here we can realize baker's hat as

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \mathcal{W}_q \\ &\Rightarrow \mathcal{S}_\sigma^x \cdot \mathcal{L}_\xi^{xx} \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial M_2}{}^E \end{aligned}$$

With big thanks to ξ , the example

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \Psi_{z\zeta} \\ &\Leftarrow \Psi_{z\zeta} \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Enumerating Driver Toward an Exponent of Arithmetic

$$\begin{aligned} &(F(\xi))_{(F(\xi))}^{-1} \zeta \\ &(F(\xi))^{F(\xi)-1} \zeta \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{P(\xi_t)}{(\zeta)} \\ &(F(\xi))^{z-1} \xi \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial y} \\ &\Rightarrow \exp \int (\alpha z dz). \\ &\Rightarrow \mathcal{R}_g \left(\frac{\partial 1}{\partial Y} \mathcal{R} \left(\frac{\partial 1}{\partial W} \bar{\theta} (\mathcal{R}_{\bar{z}}^\xi(\xi))^{-1} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Here we construct only for the natural individuality of $\xi = (\partial/\partial\xi)$ and $\partial/\partial\xi$ as bellow